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D4.2 – Training plan

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1. Executive Summary

BioExcel runs an innovative training programme that truly adapts to the user's needs. The programme is based on a competency profile and the identification of areas with low coverage of training opportunities (BioExcel or third-party). To increase the impact of our offering we collaborate with other HPC training organisations (e.g. PRACE) and expose all training resources we are aware of to our community through the Knowledge Resource Center.

As HPC continues to become more vital to life science research we need to continue to lower the barrier to adoption and support the capacity building of our community. We have extended our training offer with remote training, which has allowed us to broaden our reach, increase the variety of the content we offer and made our training programme more accessible.

This document describes the updated BioExcel competency profile and the training activities completed in 2019. It includes an evaluation of the virtual training pilots and our future plans to incorporate these sessions into the BioExcel training programme. Long-term impact from previous BioExcel courses is also presented.

The BioExcel competency profile has been updated to version 2, with substantial changes being made to condense and streamline the profile for ease of use. The existing learning resources were remapped to the new version of the framework at the level of the Knowledge, Skills and Attitudes (KSAs). 225 learning resources are now mapped to version 2 of the BioExcel competency profile and available in the Knowledge Resource Center.

Four virtual training pilot courses have been run successfully. This form of delivery is clearly an excellent way of increasing the reach of the BioExcel training programme and we have already four courses planned in early 2020. We discuss the challenges these sessions pose and how we will address them. We present a set of guidelines for preparing and delivering virtual courses, which will be further developed during the rest of the BioExcel project.

We describe an overview of the face to face training events completed in 2019 and discuss the feedback received through post-course surveys. 100% of respondents gave one of the two top ratings to the three reported courses where a question regarding an overall rating was included. In addition to the events organised by BioExcel training work package, the BioExcel partners have participated in 12 training activities listed in this report. BioExcel will continue to deliver training to the biomolecular research community through already planned events listed here and others yet to be confirmed.

The long-term impact of previous training activities is also described here. It shows that most respondents use the skills gained during the courses and many of them teach others, which broadens the impact that our training has in the community.

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2. BioExcel Competency Profile

The BioExcel Training programme is based on a competency profile; this profile allows us to define the competencies that users of BioExcel need to develop, to enable them to fully exploit the applications and services provided by BioExcel. A competency is an observable ability of any professional, integrating multiple components such as knowledge, skills and attitudes (KSAs), these components are also called attributes.

The key aspects of the competency-based approach are:

- Competencies are observable, so acquisition can be validated objectively
- Evidence of competency can be collected in a competency portfolio
- Competencies are shared ‘currency’ applicable to learning of all types and at all career stages

During the previous phase of BioExcel each competency was mapped to training already provided by the BioExcel partners (and selected third-party resources) to create a matrix, which allowed us to identify gaps, and areas of high training needs. This information is essential to develop courses that enable the community to acquire the required competencies. Using the mapping and the gap analysis ensures that our training programme has a high impact, as it adapts to actual needs of the user. The BioExcel training programme specifically focuses on the training needs areas, where currently available training resources are not providing sufficient coverage (e.g. Hands-on Introduction to HPC for Life Scientists), as well as areas where we can deliver added value by providing training across multiple resources (e.g. BioExcel Summer school or BioExcel/PRACE Seasonal School).

Competency profiles are not meant to be static documents, but updated over time, in this document we present the second version of the BioExcel profile. Our experience in the first phase of BioExcel has taught us that the usability of the competency profile is predominantly at the level of the attributes (KSAs), and that the full profile can be overwhelmingly complex. We have therefore worked to make the second version more specific to BioExcel, reduce the number of competencies and cleaned up and consolidated the number of KSAs per competency. The existing learning resources were remapped to the new version of the profile but at the level of the KSAs to make the profile more user friendly.

2.1. BioExcel Competency profile version 2

In table 1, we show a side-by-side comparison of version 1 and version 2 of the BioExcel competency profile at the level of the competencies to show the evolution of the profile.

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The competency profile has been significantly condensed, according to the following actions:

- **Deprecated:** if the training needs analysis were felt to be outside the core activity area of BioExcel. In the case of deprecated competencies all content is discarded, including the associated KSAs.
- **Dissolved:** in case of partially duplicated across competencies, and/or the content is considered to be more suitable to the KSA level or moved to another competency.
- **Content expanded:** competency has gained new content, either at competency or attribute level.
- **Moved:** competency moved to a different domain
- **Merged:** two or more competencies have been (partially) merged together
- **Reworded:** content has stayed the same but was reworded.

Note that all competencies have been revised at the level of the attributes (KSAs), this was essential to allow mapping of learning resources at the KSA level rather than competency level only.

Version 2 of the BioExcel competency profile now has 17 competencies across three domains: Scientific (5), Computing (6) and Parallel Computing (6).

Competencies V.1	Changes from version 1 to version 2	Competencies V.2
1. Generic Competencies	Deprecated	
[1.1] Function effectively in teams to accomplish a common goal.	Deprecated	
[1.2] Comprehend and comply with professional, ethical, legal, security, and social issues and responsibilities, and uphold these in the workplace as appropriate.	Deprecated	
[1.3] Communicate effectively with a range of audiences, technical and nonprofessional.	Deprecated	
[1.4] Engage in continuing professional development (CPD).	Deprecated	
[1.5] Identification and understanding of user needs.	Content expanded and moved from Generic (1.5) to Scientific domain (Sc_2)	
Scientific Competencies		Scientific
[2.1] Apply computing expertise appropriate to the discipline and level of expertise (software as well as hardware).	Dissolved, elements merged into C_1	

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[2.2] Apply expertise in formal & natural sciences appropriate to the discipline.	Content expanded with elements from 2.3	[Sc_1] Apply expertise in formal & natural sciences appropriate to the discipline, and follow best practice in experimental design
	Content expanded and moved from Generic (1.5) to Scientific domain (Sc_2)	[Sc_2] User-driven service provision and support
[2.3] Detailed comprehension of the scientific process and an ability to apply it (e.g. experimental design; inclusion of controls; QA, QC, processing, visualisation and interpretation of results).	Dissolved, elements merged into Sc_1	
[2.4] Comprehension of, and compliance with, licensing policy.	Moved to computing domain (C_5)	
[2.5] Use a computer-based system, process, component, or program to meet desired needs in a biomolecular context.	Deprecated (duplicated in 2.6)	
[2.6] Evaluate the ability of a computer-based system, process, component, or program to meet desired needs in a biomolecular context.	2.6 and 3.2 merged and moved to Computing domain as C_1	
[2.7] Comprehension of the local and global impact of high-performance computing (HPC) and high-throughput computing (HTC) on individuals, organizations, and society.	Dissolved, elements merged into PC_4	
[2.8] Comprehension of how data-driven science, data analysis and computational modelling can be combined to generate and test hypotheses (e.g. machine learning, data mining, pattern recognition).	Unchanged	[Sc_5] Comprehension of how data-driven science, data analysis and computational modelling can be combined to generate and test hypotheses (e.g. machine learning, data mining, pattern recognition).
[2.9] Identify and compile appropriate data sets to address specific research questions	2.9 and 2.12 merged to form Sc_3	[Sc_3] Search for, assess and compile appropriate literature and data sets to address specific research questions
[2.10] Comprehension of, and compliance with, best practice in data management / organization / archiving and storage	2.10 and 2.11 merged to form Sc_4	[Sc_4] Comprehension of, and compliance with, best practice in data management, organization, archiving and, storage and data management planning

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[2.11] Comprehension of, and compliance with, best practice in distributed data management and data management planning	2.10 and 2.11 merged to form Sc_4	
[2.12] Search for, read and assess literature / manual	2.9 and 2.12 merged to form Sc_3	
[2.13] Presenting your results to community (writing papers, conference presentation, YouTube)	Deprecated	
Generic Computing Competencies		Computing
[3.1] Comprehension of, and compliance with, good programming practice (as promoted, for example, by www.software-carpentry.org).	3.1, 3.4 and 3.5 merged to form C_3	
[3.2] Analyze a problem and identify and define the computing requirements appropriate to its solution (e.g., define algorithmic time and space complexities and hardware resources required to solve a problem).	2.6 and 3.2 merged and maintained in Computing domain as C_1	[C_1] Analyze a problem and identify and define the computing requirements appropriate to its solution (e.g., define algorithmic time and space complexities and hardware resources required to solve a problem).
[3.3] Apply knowledge of the operating system.	Unchanged	[C_2] Apply knowledge of the operating system.
[3.4] Write/adapt computer programs (software development) for biomolecular simulations.	3.1, 3.4 and 3.5 merged to form C_3	[C_3] Write/adapt scripts and computer programs (software development) for biomolecular simulations in compliance with good programming practice
[3.5] Write his/her own scripts to perform tasks in context of biomolecular research.	3.1, 3.4 and 3.5 merged to form C_3	
[3.6] Install biomolecular simulation software on his/her computer.	3.6 and 3.7 merged to form C_4	[C_4] Install or deploy biomolecular simulation software on his/her computer or server.
[3.7] Deploy and test non-commercial software, including software that is built collaboratively and on a volunteer basis.	3.6 and 3.7 merged to form C_4	
	Moved to computing domain (C_5)	[C_5] Comprehension of, and compliance with, licensing policy.
[3.8] Apply knowledge of systems monitoring (e.g. queue monitoring, systems availability and optimisation,	Competency reworded, element moved to KSA level	[C_6] Apply knowledge of systems monitoring (e.g. queue monitoring, systems

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storage used; scheduling maintenance at appropriate times and communicating this to users).		availability and optimisation, storage used)
Parallel Computing Competencies		Parallel Computing
[4.1] Assess computational workflow systems and their potential benefits.	Unchanged	[PC_1] Assess computational workflow systems and their potential benefits.
[4.2] Apply knowledge of batch system	Unchanged	[PC_2] Apply knowledge of batch system
[4.3] Write computer programs that can run on a parallel computer	Unchanged	[PC_3] Write computer programs that can run on a parallel computer
[4.4] Assess advantages and limitations for deploying, executing and optimising computations in a cloud/grid/HPC environment	Elements from 2.7 added to 4.4 (now PC_4)	[PC_4] Assess advantages and limitations for deploying, executing and optimising computations in a cloud/grid/HPC environment
[4.5] Apply knowledge of performance profiling to measure suitability of computing platforms	Unchanged	[PC_5] Apply knowledge of performance profiling to measure suitability of computing platforms

Table 1: Side by side comparison of version 1 and version 2 of the BioExcel competency profile and description of the changes made between the versions. Colour code: Red = deprecated (incl. KSAs), Grey = dissolved, some content retained, Yellow = new content gained, Blue = moved to different domain, Green = competencies merged, Purple = competency reworded.

2.2. Competency mapper & Knowledge Resource Centre

The Competency mapper is a web-based tool to support the creation and management of competency frameworks for professionals working in the biomolecular sciences (<https://competency.ebi.ac.uk/>). The competency mapper is being developed by the EMBL-EBI training team. It currently holds five competency frameworks, with the BioExcel competency framework as its primary use case. Competency frameworks were designed to be used by the training communities who developed them, and openly available to anyone who might find them useful, yet all too often they end up buried in a PDF file as part of a project deliverable. This made the EMBL-EBI training team long for a web-based tool that would make these frameworks, and the training associated with them, readily discoverable. We therefore decided to build that tool, and although it's still in the early stages of development we've decided to make it openly available now so that we can seek broad input to improve it and make it as useful as possible to the education and training community at large.

The competency mapper has been extended to allow versioning of the competency profile. The second version of the BioExcel competency profile has been added to the competency mapper

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(<https://competency.ebi.ac.uk/framework/bioexcel/2.0>). Previous versions are accessible at the bottom of the page in a static version. When a new version is created in the competency mapper, release notes are added to describe what changes have been made to the profile and why. The recent upgrades to the Competency Mapper mean that it is now directly connected to the BioExcel Knowledge Resource Center (<http://krc.bioexcel.eu/>) by an API that supplies the latest version of the competency profile, training resources, mapping and at a future stage the reference user profiles (milestone M13 at PM18 - see future development plans).

The BioExcel Knowledge Resource Center (KRC) is the primary portal for BioExcel users to explore the BioExcel competency profile and find relevant training resources. The beta version has been replaced with a new front-end that provides close integration with the EMBL-EBI Competency Mapper and an improved user interface.

The updated mapping and list of training resources is available through the KRC. We currently have 225 training resources available in it.

2.2.1. Future development plans

We have ambitious future development plans for the competency mapper and KRC, which will move them into the area of career development, capacity building and add learning pathways to our training offer.

Reference user profiles are representations of fictitious members of the BioExcel community, that have been rated against the BioExcel competency profile; for example, a Research Software Engineer, or System Administrator in an HPC centre. The aim is to allow members of the community to create their own user profile (with a rating against the competency profile), to enable self-assessment for the purpose of professional development, but also to enable them to overlap their own rating of the BioExcel competencies with the ratings of the reference user profiles to inform their career development options.

We anticipate using the concept of the reference user profile as a starting point for our learning pathways. The learning pathways will start from a reference user profile that has a learning challenge they need to overcome, and we provide a curated set of learning resources available in the Knowledge Resource Centre to overcome this challenge. Creation of the initial learning pathways will be driven by the results of the training needs analysis, but our long-term aim is to also learn directly from the user profiles created by members of the BioExcel community to build additional learning pathways that are adapted to current and changing user needs. We anticipate that this will provide a powerful method for BioExcel to learn what new resources (both training and software resources) should be developed based on the needs of the community.

3. Evaluation of the Virtual Training Pilots

Here we present the pilot courses carried out in the last months to assess the tools and setup to use in our virtual training programme. We explain the setup of the courses and the feedback that we received from participants. We also discuss specific challenges that we encountered and how we will tackle them.

3.1. Previous relevant course

Part of our plan is to offer virtual training in the codes that BioExcel develops. Running biomolecular modelling and simulation has high computational demands and therefore we cannot rely on running this on the participants' computers. During BioExcel-1, the BioExcel Cloud Portal was successfully used to deploy virtual machines (VMs) at training events, such as the *Joint MuG-BioExcel Workshop: Multiscale Nucleic Acids Simulations*, which took place in Barcelona in 2018.

During the event, participants connected to the BioExcel Cloud Portal to run a series of tools for multiscale genomics modelling and simulation through the command line. It was the first test for our Cloud Portal, and it proved to be a powerful tool for training events. The Cloud Portal was able to deploy and sustain one virtual machine per student, a total of 20.

From that experience, we learned that we need to make the access to the Portal simpler, as it required that people got Elixir credentials, access to the BioExcel team and permissions for deploying VMs. The latter could only be given by one person at EMBL-EBI. Once they got the access, participants were able to follow the instructions on the tutorials exercises if they had basic Linux skills. After that experience, access to the BioExcel team has been streamlined and we are working on allowing the trainer to give permission for deploying VMs, so that this process does not require the participation of anyone outside the course. In case we need VMs, we would ask participants to set up their account in the Portal before the training session. We have not run any remote course using this setup yet, but we have tested the BioExcel Portal. Several of the partners who will deliver virtual training have been able to connect to the Portal, deploy VMs and run workflows in them. We plan a course about Common Workflow Language (CWL) at the beginning of 2020 where we will use VMs.

3.2. Virtual training pilots

We have delivered four pilot courses using different setups and online tools. For these pilot courses, we only accepted a limited number of participants between 8 and 10, on a first-come, first-served basis. Below, there is a description of each of the courses: *Using Twitter to promote your project*, *The Unix Shell*, *Making sense of PDB data with PDBe-KB* and *Computational biomolecular simulation workflows with BioExcel building blocks*.

3.2.1. Using Twitter to promote your project

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3.2.1.1. SESSION OUTLINE

The course introduced the inner workings of Twitter and discussed how to create content in Twitter and how to increase the visibility of your posts. It also covered Twitter analytics, Twitter best practice and how Twitter is best used when you are using it as part of a team

This course was delivered as a single 2.5 h online session through GoToTraining. It consisted of a combination of lecturing by two trainers and activities where participants worked on a document shared through GoToTraining, both individually and in groups. During the whole session, participants could ask questions and discuss with the trainers.

3.2.1.2. PARTICIPATION AND FEEDBACK

After the online session finished, the 8 participants (3 males, 5 females) in this course received a feedback survey to complete, which they all did. On a scale of 5, where 5 is best, they all rated the course as 4 or 5. Among the best part of the course, they mentioned: the basic introduction to Twitter, good tips discussed, hands-on activity, introduction to Tweetdeck and Twitter metrics. When asked about the worst part of the course, the response was unanimously related to the second activity, where they were divided into two groups. Some of them mentioned technical problems, others lack of time.

We also asked participants how often they used Twitter and most of them (88%) replied “never” or “less than once a week”. When asked whether they would use it more often now, 38 % replied “yes” and 62% replied “maybe”, while nobody said “no”.

Some attendees experienced technical problems during the session when accessing the activities. We approached them individually to learn more about the issues and be able to avoid them next time. From this, we learned that we will need to ask participants to use Google Chrome as the web browser to join our remote sessions if they include an activity on a shared document.

Overall, the course went well and most of the comments that participants added to the last open question of the survey were positive. We are aware of the issue with the second activity. The session ran for longer than expected, so there was not enough time to carry out the collaborative work required for it. In future editions of the course, the session will be planned so that there is enough time for the activity, as participants valued positively the hands-on activities.

3.2.1.3. SPECIFIC CHALLENGES

A general challenge in online training is how to achieve social interaction between the participants, as it lacks the face to face element. In this course, participants

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were invited to ask questions and discuss during the session and several of them did it. In addition to this, there were two planned activities during the session, where participants had to work on a shared document. The technology works well to deliver group activities, but only if the participants have the right technical requirements, so we need to be aware of this and ask for it when we announce the courses.

For the second activity, participants were divided into two groups. It was an activity designed for them to discuss and agree on what to answer and share with the rest. However, the session was running out of time and there were only three minutes left for the activity, which was too short. From the feedback responses, participants valued the possibility to carry out hands-on activities, so we will plan the next session with more time for this.

Apart from having the right tools and an adequate amount of time, it will be important to keep the number of participants low (maximum around 10) in order to ensure interaction among them in a course like this. We should still be able to reach a good number of participants by delivering the course regularly, which is affordable in an online setup.

3.2.2. The Unix Shell

3.2.2.1. SESSION OUTLINE

This course was an introduction to the Unix shell for people who had no or very little experience with a command line interface. It was based on a Software Carpentry lesson covering the basics of file systems and the shell. The course was specifically aimed at life scientists, so it included relevant examples for them. Lack of working knowledge of the command line interface is still a common barrier to using HPC, especially for Life Scientists.

The course consisted of two online sessions of approximately 1 hour of duration, run using Blackboard Collaborate. In these sessions, the trainer gave some explanations about the shell, showed how to work with the command line and made participants try some commands on their own computers. The online sessions were on Monday and Friday. Between the two sessions, participants had time to follow the Software Carpentry lesson on their own at their own pace. They could email any questions they had to the trainers and also ask them during the second session on Friday.

3.2.2.2. PARTICIPATION AND FEEDBACK

All 10 participants who registered for the course (8 females, 2 males) attended the first online session and only 4 attended the second online session. All of them received a link to a feedback survey after the end of the course. 2 people replied to it. On a scale of 5, where 5 is best, they rated the course as 3 and 4. Among the

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best from the course, they mentioned: the material provided, the clarity of explanations and the fact that the trainer was demonstrating what to do on his own terminal. Among the worst: lack of time during the sessions and during the week for working on the activities and that the trainer explained rather advanced aspects about the shell.

One of them had used the Unix shell occasionally before and the other one had not used it. Both said that they would use it in the future. When asked whether they would recommend the course, one of them replied “yes”, while the other one replied “maybe”.

From these two respondents, the course went well. We can adjust the time and the level of what is explained for next time. However, most of the participants in the course did not attend the second session and we do not know the causes for that, as we only got responses from 2 people. In a future edition of this course, we will increase the level of interaction during the first session and see if that increases the participants in the second one.

3.2.2.3. SPECIFIC CHALLENGES

As the audience for this course are beginners in the use of the shell, one of the main challenges is to keep the sessions and exercises at a basic level that everybody can follow. Participants liked the software carpentry lesson followed in the course, so it would be good to follow it as much as possible in the online sessions.

The main aim of this course is that participants get familiar with the shell, so they need to work on their own machines. In a face to face course, if they have an issue, a trainer can go next to them, look at their screen and help them. It would be ideal to have the possibility of sharing the screen in a 1:1 setup that mimics the face to face situation, but the tools that we have tried so far do not provide that option. We will investigate whether we can find a tool which allows us to do this, as it might also be useful for other courses.

There was not much interaction between the participants and the trainer or among the participants, except for a couple of questions from participants during the first session. Increasing the level of interaction might enhance the learning experience and therefore we will include some activity where participants discuss about the concepts they are learning, and we will encourage them to ask questions during each session and between the sessions. It is good that participants get practice with the shell on their own, so we don't consider necessary to reach the same level of social interaction as in the Twitter course.

There was a lack of time during the sessions, so in the future, we will run this course with more time at least in one of the two online sessions. This should allow for both longer explanations where needed and more interactivity.

3.2.3. Making sense of PDB data with PDBe-KB

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3.2.3.1. SESSION OUTLINE

This course was an introduction to PDBe Knowledge Base (PDBe-KB), a new, community-based resource which brings together PDB data and functional annotations in innovative ways. It was aimed at people who work on proteins or protein-related data and would like to find structural data to help support their work.

The session was delivered through GoToTraining. It consisted of a presentation of about 35 minutes from the trainer and three activities where participants worked in small groups to get practice on using the various pages and sections of the PDBe-KB. This includes aggregated views of proteins with information about structural coverage, ligand interaction sites, protein-protein contacts, and functional annotations from a range of external databases.

During the tasks, participants had the chance to ask questions to the trainer. After each task, they received feedback from the trainer and had the opportunity to discuss with everybody in the session. In total, the time spent in the activities was approximately 1 hour and a half.

3.2.3.2. PARTICIPATION AND FEEDBACK

10 participants registered for this course (100% registration rate) and 5 more interested people were added to a waiting list. 2 of these were allowed to participate in the session after two people cancelled their registration. 6 people joined the session at some point (3 males and 3 females), but most of them left when we started the activities. We started the first one with 4 people, the second one with 3 people and the last one with 2 people (a third one joined for some time). During the last discussion of the session, one of the participants said, “big thank you” and that it had been “very instructive” and “extremely helpful”.

All the participants who joined the session received a feedback survey after the session. 2 people replied to it. On a scale of 5, where 5 is best, they rated the course as 3 and 4. When asked about the best of the course, both mentioned the practical exercises in the breakout sessions. Only one of them replied to what the worst was and mentioned technical problems in the beginning of the session. Both said that they would recommend the course and that they would use PDBe-KB, which they had not done before the course.

From the trainer’s perspective, the interactive sessions went really well, and they could see that the participants worked with interest in the tasks provided and they raised very good points during the discussions.

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3.2.3.3. SPECIFIC CHALLENGES

One of the main challenges for our virtual training programme is to get interaction among participants and between the trainer and the participants. In this session, everybody thinks that the interactivity was successful.

The main issue in this session was that people did not join or left before the end of the session, especially when the activities started. We do not know why this happened, but low turnout usually happens in courses delivered for free. In future editions, we will consider allowing more people to register, so that we still have a good number for the session. We need to think carefully about how many more we register, as we would like to have a number of participants that we can manage through breakout classrooms and interactive sessions. Even though here 40% of registrants did not join the course, we might consider allowing 20% or 30% more in future editions and only increase that number if it is consistent that close to half of the registrants do not turn out.

3.2.4. **Computational biomolecular simulation workflows with BioExcel building blocks**

3.2.4.1. SESSION OUTLINE

This course was an introduction to the [BioExcel building blocks](#) (biobb), a fully interoperable software library comprising a collection of Python wrappers on top of biomolecular simulation tools such as GROMACS, Ambertools, Openbabel or ACPYPE. It was aimed at people starting computational biomolecular simulation and building computational biomolecular simulations workflows. Familiarity with molecular dynamics and minimum Linux skills were required to join.

Before the course, participants received instructions to install two biobb tutorials through bioconda packages so that they could work with the library in their own computers according to the trainer's instructions.

The training event consisted of two sessions delivered through GoToTraining, 3 hours long each. At the end of the first session, attendees received a series of tasks to work on and explore the biobb library. They could email the trainers with questions before the second session.

The trainer introduced the library and the principles behind it and then presented and explained workflows implemented in Jupyter notebooks (e.g. protein-ligand complex GROMACS MD setup). Participants could follow in their own machines and ask the trainer if they had any issues.

The second session started with a discussion and demonstration of the tasks given at the end of the first session. Most participants took part in the discussion. After this, the first steps on how to build and run complex workflows in command-line were explored.

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3.2.4.2. PARTICIPATION AND FEEDBACK

For this course, we increased our registration limit, after the low attendance rate observed in the previous virtual training event. 19 people registered for the course. 10 of them (1 female, 9 males) joined the sessions at some point. Of the 6 people who stayed until the end of the first session, 4 joined the second one, where we also had 3 other attendees. Several of them emailed the trainers with questions about the installation and about the tasks to do, which shows that they engaged with the course content.

The 10 people who joined the sessions received a feedback survey after the course. 3 of them replied to it and rated the course as 4 (2 people) and 5, the two best scores in the given scale. They all said that they would recommend this training event. When asked about the best part of the course, they mentioned the hands-on activities and the way the trainer interacted with them during the sessions. As the worst, they mentioned limited time and the fast pace in the last part of the course. In future iterations of this course, we will run it in 3 sessions, so that people have more time to work with the biobb between sessions. In the open comments section, we received a very encouraging comment, as one of the reasons for doing remote courses is to increase the reach of our training programme: “Being a guy from the third world, who wants to learn molecular modeling by myself, such training is all that we wish for. Kudos to BioExcel”.

In addition to the positive interaction with participants during the course, the trainers also obtained valuable feedback for the future development of the BioExcel building blocks.

3.2.4.3. SPECIFIC CHALLENGES

This was the first course where we asked participants to install software before joining. For this, we sent step-by-step instructions to the registered participants and allowed them to ask questions to the trainers in case they had any issue. The trainers were able to solve most of them and learned from this, so that they will be able to write more precise instructions and anticipate some of the problems next time, as there are some differences depending on the computers used by participants.

During the sessions, attendees could follow what the trainer did on their own machines, like in the course about Unix. But in this case, the interaction worked well: they could interrupt the trainer and ask questions and they did; in addition, the trainer stopped several times during the session to check that they were following with short questions that could be answered on the chat (see example in the appendix). For this course, it would be helpful that participants could share their screen 1:1 with the trainers in case they have any issue. This would make the

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session more similar to a face-to-face situation where you can approach someone and help them on their computers.

The participants who attended the first session until the end worked on the suggested tasks and tried the biobb library, so they had some questions in the beginning of the second session. This is very valuable for their learning experience and we think that it would be really good to have the same opportunity after learning how to run complex workflows from the command line. Therefore, for the next iteration of this course, we will schedule it in three sessions with time in between for them to work on their own with support from the trainers if needed.

3.3. Analysis

The pilot virtual sessions were extremely valuable to learn what we would like to carry forward into the main BioExcel training programme and which challenges we need to address when we develop future courses:

- 1) Combining hands-on activities and lectures.
- 2) Structure the documents for hands-on activities.
- 3) GoToTraining is our platform of choice for course delivery.
- 4) Need to work on numbers of registrants/attendees.
- 5) Computational tools and demands.

These topics are discussed in detail below. We started developing a set of guidelines for trainers with specific recommendations for virtual training (see appendix), which will be updated when our experience with virtual training grows.

- 1) Combining hands-on activities and lectures.

In an online environment, it can be difficult to achieve social interactions between the participants and with the trainers. In the courses delivered so far, we managed to combine lectures and hands-on activities for the attendees, both individual and in groups. The feedback regarding these activities has been very positive and we will continue working to keep a high level of interaction in our virtual training sessions to enhance the learning experience.

- 2) Structure the documents for hands-on activities.

From the experience with these pilot courses and the feedback from both trainers and participants, we think that it is important to provide detailed instructions and structured documents for the hands-on tasks, so that trainees can focus on the activity itself and not waste time finding out what to do (example in the appendix).

- 3) GoToTraining is our platform of choice for course delivery.

We tested two online platforms for delivering the live sessions: Blackboard Collaborate and GoToTraining. Both of them worked well for delivering presentations and sharing the trainer's screen. Both platforms allow the creation of breakout rooms where participants can work in small groups, but we have only tested GoToTraining for this collaborative work. This is due to a limited number

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of courses delivered so far and the fact that GoToTraining allows participants to work on a shared Google document that is saved afterwards. This document is also available for the trainer to share with all participants, enabling groups discussion about the hands-on activities. The EMBL-EBI training team has a GoToTraining account that is available for future training sessions and internal expertise in how to use the platform. In Blackboard Collaborate people can work on a shared whiteboard or share their screen, files or applications, but nothing is saved, so additional instructions are needed in order to share/save the output of the breakout session. For now, we will use GoToTraining, but if we consider carrying out different kinds of activities where we might need other functionalities, we will re-evaluate this decision and explore other platforms.

4) Need to work on numbers of registrants/attendees.

Another challenge that we face in the delivery of virtual courses, especially when offered for free as was the case for the pilot sessions, is that we do not know how many people will actually join the session (though they have registered in advance); this is similar to the high no-show rate seen in free face-to-face courses. For the pilot sessions, we aimed to keep the attendee numbers low in order to achieve successful interactions, however, in the future we will have to carefully consider how many registrants we accept per course. We will monitor the turnout rate in all our courses to assess the most appropriate maximum. We will also consider charging a fee or a no-show fee, as this will strengthen the registrant's commitment.

5) Computational tools and demands.

Training on biomolecular simulation requires the use of specific software, so for some courses, we will need participants to download and install the tools that will be used during the sessions. We need to send clear instructions for doing this. Bioconda packages, as the ones used in our last pilot session, or containers can simplify the process as everything needed for the training can be downloaded and installed together, but any required instructions for the specific container software need to be included.

Finally, training on biomolecular simulation software and tools has high computational demands, so it might not be possible that participants run it on their own computers. To address this, we have the possibility of deploying virtual machines through the cloud portal, which will be needed for some of our future training events. We will use them in the course about the Common Workflow Language in the beginning of 2020. In some other occasions, it might be worth to give participants access to a large European HPC machine, as we do in some of our face to face training events. We will consider this possibility if required for some course in the future.

3.4. Conclusion and future plans

After the four pilot courses, it is clear that virtual sessions add value to our training programme as they allow us to offer a wider variety of courses that we would not be able to deliver face-to-face (e.g. *Using Twitter to promote your project*). These

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courses also extend the reach of the programme, as the remote delivery lowers the barriers for attendance.

We will continue delivering remote training sessions in the future, as we have seen that they are well received by the participants. In order to extend our reach even further and to gain valuable feedback information from more people, we will scale the sessions up and run them with a higher number of participants.

We will repeat some of the courses already delivered and develop more advanced ones for the same topics (e.g. Twitter, the Unix shell). We will add other courses, including training on BioExcel software packages.

The following courses are planned in the next few months:

- *Using Twitter to promote your project.* 31 January 2020 (course already oversubscribed).
- *Introduction to Common Workflow Language.* January or February 2020, exact date to be confirmed.
- *Using Twitter to promote your project.* 28 February 2020.
- *ResOps: Cloud-native tools and technology for researchers.* 24 to 28 February 2020 (4 sessions).

During the pilot phase, our courses were mainly announced internally. From January, we will announce all the virtual courses on our website and promote them through social media, as we do with any other BioExcel event.

4. Training Programme

4.1. Seasonal school 2019 - HPC MD Simulations with GROMACS, AMBER, NAMD and VMD

4.1.1. Course overview

After receiving great feedback from the first edition in 2017, we organized for the second time a seasonal school jointly with PRACE (<https://bioexcel.eu/events/bioexcel-prace-seasonal-school-2019-sweden-hpc-for-life-sciences/>). As in the previous edition, we invited the main developers of some of the most popular and well-known applications for molecular modelling and simulations – GROMACS, AMBER, NAMD and VMD. This is a unique event where all four are part of the same training course. The school took place at KTH in Stockholm between 10-13 June 2019. Over the 4 days of the event, the school program allowed participants to get a comprehensive understanding of the usage of the different simulation and visualization codes; their scalability and performance, as well as ways to avoid potential issues; learn the best practices about using them on HPC systems. Extensive hands-on sessions covered more than half of the time during the school.

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4.1.2. Conclusion and course feedback

62 applications for the seasonal school were received, of which 57 were accepted, and a total of 8 applicants requested a travel grant to support their participation in the course, of which 3 were granted. The gender balance of the students at the course was 61% male (35/57) and 39% female (22/57), and the gender balance of the faculty and support staff was 25% female and 75% male.

The feedback response percentage was 32%, but not all respondents completed the survey. We asked them how useful (on a scale 1 to 5) they found each session of the school. Most people rated the sessions between 3 and 5. The highest rated lecture was the one about GROMACS with 13 (72%) people rating it with a 5. The hands-on sessions got more variable ratings than the lectures, with the GROMACS one being also the highest scored: 39% rated it with a 5 and 28% with a 4. When asked about the best of each section, participants mentioned, among others: the chance of interacting with the software developers, useful tips given, the possibility of working in multiple tutorials. They also made suggestions about what to improve, e.g. making it more HPC focused, which we will consider for future editions of the course. They valued very positively the overall organisation of the course, 89% scored it as 4 or 5.

One of the real challenges in providing realistic training in using High Performance Computing is giving a classroom of people access to large HPC resources. A scenario where ~50 students require HPC access of 10-20 nodes each, this will require some ~1000 nodes reserved for a training school. There is a clear need for CoEs to get access to HPC resources for the purpose of training.

We will consider running the school again in collaboration with PRACE.

4.2. BioExcel Summer School on Biomolecular Simulations 2019

4.2.1. Course overview

For the second year running, BioExcel delivered the BioExcel Summer School on Biomolecular Simulations (<https://bioexcel.eu/events/bioexcel-summer-school-on-biomolecular-simulations-2019/>), the course took place from Sunday 30th June to Friday 5th July 2019 at the Science and Technology Park of Sardinia, Pula, Italy. The summer school included lectures and hands-on sessions on molecular dynamics simulations, biomolecular docking, QM/MM, Free energy calculations and advanced sampling methods (metadynamics). During the hands-on computer practicals students made use, among others, of the BioExcel flagship software (GROMACS, HADDOCK, PMX and CP2K). The summer school is intended for researchers (primarily PhD and postdocs) using or planning to use biomolecular modeling and simulation in their everyday research. Familiarity with Linux and some basic knowledge of molecular modelling software is a requirement.

4.2.2. Conclusion and course feedback

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50 applications for the summer school were received, 11 applicants did not submit the supplementary information (supervisor support letter, motivational letter), and a total of 17 applicants requested a travel grant to support their participation in the course. A total of 28 students attended the summer school, a number of cancellations were received for various reasons (financial, visa rejection, etc.), where possible the available place was offered to an applicant on the waiting list. The gender balance of the students at the course was 54% male (15/28) and 46% female (13/28), and the gender balance of the faculty was 17% female and 83% male (not taking into account research highlight presentations from the attendees).

The feedback response percentage was 77%, though not all participants completed the full survey. When asked for an overall rating of the course, 100% of the respondents replied with “Very good” (68%) and “Excellent” (32%). 89% of the respondents replied that the balance of theoretical and practical content across the workshop was “About right”, the remaining respondents were equally split between “Too practical” and “Too theoretical”. When asked “Will you use the tools or data resources covered in the workshop in your future work?” 95% respondents replied “Yes”, and the remaining 5% “Maybe”. 100% of the respondents would recommend future BioExcel workshops to colleagues. Highlights mentioned were the network opportunities with both other participants and lecturers, and specific scientific sessions. There is space for improvement to other sessions and the hotel.

Due to the positive feedback, funding has been ring-fenced to run the summer school in 2020 and 2021; we anticipate both iterations to run at the Science and Technology Park of Sardinia, Pula, Italy. We expect registration for the 2020 summer school to open by the end of 2019.

4.3. Advanced GROMACS, HADDOCK + PMX Workshop

4.3.1. Course overview

This course was jointly organised by BioExcel, CSC - IT Center for Science in Espoo, Finland and PRACE and took place at CSC’s training facilities in Espoo between October 9th and 11th 2019

(<https://bioexcel.eu/events/advanced-gromacs-haddock-pmx-workshop/>).

The main focus of this course was advanced topics and compute performance. It was assumed that participants had at least basic knowledge of GROMACS and HADDOCK. Participants were given initial training material before the course for self-assessment and a basic introduction.

The course was triggered by a request from CSC to KTH, inquiring training so that users may make better use of compute-resources at the center. Thus, much of the course was tailored to give a detailed introduction to high performance computing infrastructure and how to make best use of it with BioExcel tools by choosing optimal settings and resources for the tasks on hand. Further, advanced sampling

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methods were introduced as a higher-level strategy to enhance performance. For the molecular docking, the course focused on challenging workflows that used the most complex HADDOCK features. Additionally, PMX was introduced as a method.

The overwhelming majority of local participants came from the Finnish life-science community at all career stages.

4.3.2. Conclusion and course feedback

The collaboration with CSC was very smooth, and the excellent training facilities added to an overall friendly and collaborative workshop atmosphere. Participants interactions were lively amongst each other.

There were 21 participants present at the training and 23 remote participants. The gender balance for the on-site participants was 43% (9/21) female and 57% (12/21) male; we do not have data regarding the remote attendees. 23 of them (52%) responded to the feedback survey for the course. On a scale from 1 to 5, where 5 is best, all respondents rated the course as 4 (43%) or 5 (57%). Most of them (74%) would recommend the course.

The survey included several statements that had to be rated according to the following options: *disagree completely*, *disagree*, *no strong feelings*, *agree*, *agree completely*. Regarding the statement “The lectures were clearly presented and comprehensible”; 43% of respondents chose the option *agree completely*; 39%, *agree*; 13%, *no strong feelings*; and one person chose *disagree*. For the statement “Hands-on exercises and demonstrations were a valuable contribution to the school”, the results were: 39% *agree completely*, 26% *agree* and 22% *no strong feelings*. For the statement “The pace of teaching was right”, the scale was different: *way too slow for me*, *a bit too slow*, *about right*, *a bit too fast*, *way too fast for me*. 13% marked *way too fast for me*, 48% *a bit too fast*, and 39% *about right*.

Participants were also asked how the course could be improved and the suggestions mostly mentioned focusing on fewer topics but covering them in more detail and doing more hands-on work.

In general, where they could add comments, these are very positive about the course, so it seems that there is a need for it and that the participants enjoy it. But from what we see in the survey results, there’s still some room for improvement. In future editions, we will adjust the content covered and the pace of the training.

4.4. Hands-on introduction to HPC for Life Scientists

4.4.1. Course overview

This course was jointly organised by BioExcel and PRACE and took place at the University of Birmingham between 30th October 2019 and 1st November 2019 (<https://bioexcel.eu/events/hands-on-introduction-to-hpc-for-life-scientists-2/>).

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The course introduced HPC to life science researchers, focusing on the aspects that are most important for those new to this technology to understand. It gave participants knowledge to judge how HPC can best benefit their research and equip them to go on to successfully and efficiently make use of HPC facilities in the future. The course covered basic concepts in HPC hardware, software, user environments, filesystems, and programming models. It also provided an opportunity to gain hands-on practical experience and assistance using an HPC system (ARCHER, the UK national supercomputing service) through examples drawn from the life sciences, such as biomolecular simulation.

4.4.2. Conclusion and course feedback

The course registration ran through the PRACE registration system on a first come, first served basis with the maximum capacity of the course set at 25 participants. Out of 24 registered people, 13 (54%) attended the course. The gender balance was 31=4/13% female and 69% male. Counting all the people who initially registered for the course, there were 42 % female and 58% male.

The course feedback was collected through the standard PRACE feedback form, complemented by a few additional questions to bring it in line with the BioExcel feedback form. The response rate for the feedback survey was 92%, when asked for an overall rating for the course, 100% of respondents rated the course as *Good* or *Excellent* (50% *Excellent*). All of them rated the overall organisation as *Good* or *Excellent*.

The survey included several statements that had to be rated according to the following options: *don't know*, *disagree completely*, *disagree*, *no strong feelings*, *agree*, *agree completely*. Regarding the statement “The lectures were clearly presented and comprehensible”, 58% of respondents chose the option *agree completely* and the rest, *agree*. For the statement “The pace of teaching was right”, 42% marked *agree completely*, 50% *agree*, and 8% *no strong feelings*. For the statement “Hands-on exercises and demonstrations were a valuable contribution to the school”, the results were: 50% *agree completely*, 50% *agree*.

We also asked the participants to rate different sections of the course and most people rated them as *good* or *excellent*, so none of them stood out as a clear section to improve.

When asked what they liked the most about the course, participants frequently mentioned the practicals and the exceptional attitude and knowledge of the trainers. Regarding what they liked the least, they talked about the lack of clarity about some HPC related terminology.

This is the second time that we run the course for life scientists. Overall, the course went well and participants valued the hands-on exercises, so it seems that they didn't find them too computationally focused, as in the previous edition in 2017 ([D4.6](#), BioExcel-1). We can still improve some of the lectures to make them more understandable for life scientists with no specific knowledge of computational jargon.

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4.5. Additional courses delivered

The BioExcel training programme builds on the strong commitment the BioExcel partners have to deliver high quality training to the computational biomolecular community. Here we present additional courses in which BioExcel partners have delivered training in 2019 (table 2).

Date	Event Name	Location	Participants
February 25 2019	Non-equilibrium free energy calculation training at Janssen Pharmaceutica	Beerse, Belgium	6
March 11 2019	Application of Bioinformatics in support of Precision Medicine	Paddington, UK	45
March 14 2019	Introduction to Simulation Environments for Life Sciences	Barcelona, Spain	11
March 22-23 2019	Hünfeld 2019: Workshop on Computer Simulation and Theory of Macromolecules	Hünfeld, Germany	120
April 1-2 2019	Joint CAPRI/Instruct-ERIC Workshop	Hinxton, UK	19
April 8 - 12 2019	Research to service: Planning and running a bioinformatics core facility	Izmir, Turkey	24
July 8-11 2019	PRACE-XSEDE-RIKEN International HPC Summer School, tutorials on HPC Software engineering	Kobe, Japan	60
July 08 - 13 2019	Integrative and cellular structural biology	Paris, France	25
July 24 2019	HADDOCK Workshop	Putrajaya, Malaysia	52
September 16 - 20 2019	Structural Bioinformatics	Hinxton, UK	33
September 19 2019	Seminar at Cancer Research UK: CWL - Sharing reproducible computational Analysis	Alderly Edge, UK	15

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September 21 - 29 2019	Second International Training Workshop on Multi-Scale Biophysics Computations (FIRST)	Hanoi, Vietnam	20
October 05 - 12 2019	BlmBS 2019 in Lugano	Lugano, Switzerland	30

Table 2: List of training events

4.6. Planned courses

Besides the future virtual training sessions listed in section 3.4, the following activities are planned:

- EMBO Practical Course *Integrative modelling of biomolecular interactions*, 10-15 May 2020, Izmir (Turkey) - sponsored by BioExcel. <http://meetings.embo.org/event/20-biomolecular-interactions>
- BioExcel Summer School on Biomolecular Simulations, 22-27 June 2020, Sardinia (Italy).
- Training tutorials (topics to be confirmed) during the EMBO Workshop *Advances and Challenges in Biomolecular Simulations*, 18-22 October 2020, Brno (Czech Republic).
- BioExcel Summer School on Biomolecular Simulations 2021

Other training activities with BioExcel participation will be added to our programme as soon as they are confirmed.

5. Impact

To ensure the quality of our training programme BioExcel routinely collects course feedback for all BioExcel training activities. The responses provide us with valuable information on how to improve our events and the direction of the training programme. However, these responses are generally collected on the last day of the event and therefore do not provide us with a lot of information about the long-term impact of the BioExcel training programme and tend to focus on immediate concerns (e.g. a problem with a tutorial, a session was too short or too difficult). To assess the impact of our training programme activities, we want to know if attending our training courses has had a positive impact on their research/career and whether or not they are actively using the tools that were introduced to them during the training event.

To assess the long-term impact, BioExcel sends two long-term feedback surveys to all delegates who have attended BioExcel training courses, the first one is sent approximately 6-12 months after the training event, the second survey is sent after 2 years. The surveys collect data on whether participants are using the tools they were introduced to during the training course, whether they have established collaboration, and whether they have taught others. In addition, we ask what

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impact the course has had on their research and the research of others, as well as what the best and worst parts of the course was.

Here we present long-term feedback data from courses that were delivered during the previous funding phase of BioExcel (grant agreement 675728). We sent a survey (6-12 months after the course) to the participants of the BioExcel Summer School on Biomolecular Simulations 2018, and the longer term one (2 years after the course) to participants in the following courses from 2017: BioExcel PRACE Spring School - HPC for Life Sciences, BioExcel PRACE Hands-on Introduction to HPC for Life Scientists and BioExcel Summer School 2017 - Foundation skills for HPC in computational biomolecular research.

The response rate was as follows:

Course	Number of students who received the survey	Response rate
2017 BioExcel PRACE Spring School	48	10%
2017 Hands-on Introduction to HPC	16	19%
2017 Summer School	10	20%
2018 Summer School	29	55%

Table 3: Response rate to long-term feedback surveys

5.1. Long-term feedback survey 6-12 months (BioExcel Summer School 2018)

More than half of the people who received this survey replied to it, but some of them did not complete all the questions, so that for the full analysis the response rate is actually 41%.

Many BioExcel training events teach participants how to use certain computational tools, so a direct impact that we can have is that they actively use these tools in their research. All respondents said they have applied the tools they learned about in their own research. 83% have applied molecular dynamics codes and the rest chose the option *use of other tools*.

One way in which our courses have an impact in the research community is that the participants share what they learnt to colleagues and students. The majority (58%) of the respondents have taught between 1 and 5 other people. This means that our training reaches more people than the ones who attend our courses.

Our training courses also promote networking, as they include time for participants to interact with each other and with the trainers during breaks and

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social activities. These interactions might lead to collaborations that will directly impact the research activities of the participants. In our long-term feedback survey, we asked “Did you establish any collaborations with other participants / BioExcel researchers during this course?”. 25% of respondents replied positively to that question.

We also ask our former participants if they would recommend our course, or if they have already recommended it. All respondents to this survey would recommend the course and 92% have already recommended it to someone else, which speaks extremely well about the positive experience that they had during the summer school.

In addition to a number of pre-formulated questions, we also include the following in our survey: “Please comment on the impact that the course has had on your research and the research of others”. To analyse the impact statements we try and find common themes across the participants statements. We score each statement across the commonly identified themes. As we saw that they matched the results we obtained this time, we used the same themes as in deliverable [“D4.6 - Final report on dissemination and training”](#) - of the previous funding phase of BioExcel.

Some participant statements contain more than one theme. The most commonly reported themes are “Essential to research/actively using skills” and “Gaining knowledge/skills” with 6 counts (Figure 1). These two related themes indicate that our training is successful in transmitting participants important skills for their research. In addition to this, participants reported “I taught others” and “published a paper” as outcomes from the course.

Figure 1. Analysis of the impact statements collected in the 6-12 months long-term feedback survey

5.2. Long-term feedback survey 2 years

We analysed the results of the 2 years impact survey collectively, as we do not have enough data to obtain sensible results for every course. We got 10 responses in total from three courses.

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All these respondents have used the tools explained during the courses in their own research. All of them would recommend the course, 60% has already done it. Most of them (60%) have taught others the skills learnt during the course.

As this feedback is sent after a longer time, we are interested in whether the participation in the course had an impact on their research. In addition to collaborations, here we ask about other outcomes (e.g. writing a dissertation, applying for a grant, writing a scientific article). 30% of the respondents established collaborations as a result of the course, which shows that networking during our courses can have this long-standing impact. 20% of them wrote a dissertation after their participation in the course and 40% published a paper.

Regarding other possible outcomes, 1 person replied *yes* to “Did you receive/apply for a grant after attending this course?” and 1 person replied *yes* to “Did this course lead to a change of position or other career development?”

In this survey, we also asked participants to comment on the impact on their research. Only 6 of the 10 survey respondents answered this question, but we can match some of their statements to more than one theme. The most commonly reported ones are “Essential to research/actively using skills” and “Gaining knowledge/skills” (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Analysis of the impact statements collected in the 2 years long-term feedback survey

5.3. Conclusion long-term feedback

It is difficult to quantify the long-term feedback of training activities. The best that we can do is to assess whether participants use the skills they learned during the courses, whether they passed these skills to others and whether the course contributed to the outcome of their research. The response rate to our long-term feedback surveys is not high, but this is usual for this type of surveys. At EMBL-EBI, where they have collected long-term feedback since 2010, the response rate is around 25%.

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We are pleased that, from the responses we get, participants consider that they gained knowledge and skills from the course and many of them use the skills acquired in their research. In addition, it is clear that our training programme reaches more people than the course delegates, as many of them teach others afterwards.

Our stretch KPI target for the long-term feedback is that more than 80% responses are "Useful" or "Very Useful" to their daily activities. All the respondents have applied the skills learned during the course, so for the moment this KPI target is reached. We will continue collecting long-term feedback from past and future training events to monitor the impact that we have in the community.

6. Conclusion

BioExcel's training programme is based on a competency profile, which allows us to tailor the activities to the community needs and therefore have a high impact. We are mainly involved in three types of events: face to face courses organised (or co-organised) by BioExcel, virtual training, and other events in which BioExcel partners deliver training.

We are constantly evaluating our activities in order to improve. From the experience so far, we have learned a few lessons from which we have taken the following actions to be carried on into the future:

- We have created a new version of the competency profile, more condensed and specific to the BioExcel community. In comparison with the previous version, this one is more practical and will facilitate mapping training events precisely in our Knowledge Resource Centre and defining more specifically the training needs, so that we can develop appropriate activities.
- We have successfully delivered four virtual training sessions and learned from the experience how to develop efficient remote courses. We will now include these activities in the training programme to extend its reach. We will continue learning from it and refining our guidelines for remote trainers.
- The feedback that we receive at the end of our courses is in general positive. From the responses to long-term surveys, we can see that participants obtain useful skills. All this encourages us to continue developing training events. However, there are always some items that could be better. We address the results of feedback surveys to improve our future planned courses, like the BioExcel Summer School in 2020.

In 2020, in addition to our regular training events, we will organise an EMBO Workshop for the computational biomolecular community where there will be the possibility of offering training tutorials. This will be an excellent opportunity to consolidate BioExcel as a reference in training within the community.

7. Appendix

7.1. Guidelines for trainers of remote sessions

These recommendations are to be used together with our *Train the trainer* course material and the training event guidelines developed during the previous funding phase of BioExcel (grant agreement 675728) and outlined in deliverable 4.5¹. This set of guidelines is a living document, which will be updated as we gain more experience with virtual training.

Before the course:

- Test the delivery platform to be used (full instructions are available).
- When required, send clear step-by-step instructions for software installation.
- Familiarise yourself with the attendees, if limited information is available, prepare some questions which can be asked during the session to explore their background (example 1 below).

Course delivery:

- At the beginning of the session, tell participants that they can ask questions, on the chat or through the microphone.
- Alternate between lectures and hands-on activities whenever possible.
- Use short questions or polls every now and then during your presentation to check that people are following (examples 2 and 3 below). This is more important in an online situation than in a face-to-face course, where you can see their faces.
- Structure the documents for the activities to clearly show what to do (example 4 below).
- If you use breakout rooms, give clear instructions about:
 - What will happen: participants will be divided and able to discuss among themselves/work on a shared document, the trainer won't be there, raise hands if help is needed.
 - The task they need to carry out.
- If you want participants to discuss, try to give them some questions/tasks to think about. If the activities are too methodical, the chances that they interact are lower.
- Wrap-up the activity after they finish it: comment on what they did, ask what their main challenges were...
- At the end, tell them that they will get a feedback survey once the session ends and we appreciate their feedback.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.574620>

Example 1: Questions about previous knowledge

These questions were used at the beginning of the *Computational biomolecular simulation workflows with BioExcel building blocks* training and developed by Adam Hospital. Participants replied to them in the chat and the information allowed the trainer to get an idea about the audience of the course and adjust the session to their needs.

Questions (1)

- Did you know about BioExcel center of Excellence for Computational Biomolecular Research before? (Y/N)
- Are you familiar with Biomolecular Simulations? (Y/N)
- Have you been able to install the workflows environment from the instructions? (Y/N)
- Have you tried to run them? (Y/N)
- Extend & Discuss

Please answer in the GoToTraining chat panel

Example: N Y Y N

Examples 2 & 3: Short questions during the session

These questions were used at the beginning of the *Computational biomolecular simulation workflows with BioExcel building blocks* training and developed by Adam Hospital. They check the progress of participants and some key concepts.

Questions (2)

- Did you understand what the library can do for you? (Y/N)
- Do you think it will be useful for your work/interests? (Y/N)
- Did you miss any category in the biobb packages? (Y/N)
- Extend & Discuss

Please answer in the GoToTraining chat panel

Example: Y Y Y

Questions (4)

- Have you followed so far? (Y/N)
- The concept of inputs / outputs / properties is clear? (Y/N)
- Did you encountered problems executing this part of the tutorial in the Jupyter Notebook? (Y/N)
- If yes, they have been problems with: (1.Installation, 2.NGLview, 3.GROMACS, 4.Other)
- Extend & Discuss

Please answer in the GoToTraining chat panel

Example: Y Y Y 2

D4.2 – Training plan

Example 4: Structured document for online activities

This task comes from the pilot course *Making sense of PDB data with PDBe-KB* and it was developed by David Armstrong. There's space for writing the names of participants in each breakout room, the questions are in red and the answers are structured or filled with model answers.

Identifying ligand interactions with PDBe-KB protein pages

Split into breakouts:

Breakout A:

Breakout B:

Breakout C:

Breakout D:

Assigning protein pages to groups

Links to the example PDBe-KB protein pages:

- [Prostaglandin G/H synthase 2](#)
 - Breakout:
- [Aurora kinase A](#)
 - Breakout:
- [Ribosylidihydronicotinamide dehydrogenase](#)
 - Breakout:
- [Xanthine dehydrogenase/oxidase](#)
 - Breakout:

Task 1 (ligand images):

Navigate to the ligands section of the protein page and look at the list of ligand images

- Which ones are most commonly found bound to this structure in PDB entries?
 - 1.
 - 2.
 - 3.
- Can you group these ligands based on visual similarity (i.e. they look like similar chemical structures)? Note: this does not have to accurate matching - structures with rings, structures with extended chains etc. is enough.
 - Group 1: NN ligands, e.g. XXX, description: e.g. have 2 connected ring structures.
 - Group 2: NN ligands, e.g. XXX, description:

D4.2 – Training plan

- Group 3: NN ligands, e.g. XXX, description:
- Were there any ligands that you found difficult to fit into any groups?
 - e.g.